

Peptisation of Metallic Hydroxides in Presence of Sugars.

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It is well known that in presence of some non-electrolytes like glycerol and sugars, the precipitation of many metallic hydroxides by the addition of caustic alkali to the salt solutions is often prevented. The nature of the substances formed in solution was however in doubt for many years. Graham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1862, 15, 253) considered that sucrates of copper and iron were present in the clear liquid when caustic alkali was added to a solution of copper or iron salt in presence of cane sugar. Until recently quantitative experiments in this line were wanting though many qualitative observations have been made (*Cf. Bancroft, Ind. B. A. Report on Colloid Chemistry*, p. 2). In a previous paper one of the present authors (Sen and Dhar, *Kolloid Zeit.*, 1923, 33, 193) has studied the peptisation of various hydroxides in presence of some non-electrolytes in a semi-quantitative way. Recently Kuhn and Pirsch (*Kolloid Zeit.*, 1925, 36, 310, and *Zsigmondy Festschr*) in Wo. Ostwald's laboratory have made a detailed study of the peptisation of bismuth hydroxide in presence of several sugars in the same way as Sen had previously done. As the subject is an interesting one and seems to have an important bearing on the general theory of peptisation, it was considered desirable to undertake some more quantitative work in this connection. The peptisation of copper, mercury, iron and cerium hydroxides has been studied in presence of sucrose, dextrose, lævulose and lactose in various concentrations, and an account of these experiments is given in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Semi-normal solutions of the chlorides of the metals (except that of mercury which was one third normal) were prepared. The standard solution of mercuric chloride was prepared by weighing out the required quantity of the salt; those of copper, cerium and ferric chloride were made by diluting strong standard

solutions in which copper was standardised against thiosulphate, and iron and cerium were estimated gravimetrically. Solutions of sugars (Kahlbaum's pure chemicals) were also prepared by weighing. The solutions were all molar except that of milk sugar which was usually semimolar. A seminormal caustic soda, free from carbonate as much as possible, was prepared to form the hydroxides of the metals. The amount of alkali added was always in excess of that required to form completely the hydroxide of the metal. The minimum amount of any sugar necessary to prevent the formation of a visible precipitate was found out as follows.

A known volume of the salt solution under investigation was measured out from a pipette graduated into a hundredth of a c.c. and mixed with varying amounts of sugar solutions in test tubes. In other test tubes a definite amount of alkali was diluted with calculated amounts of distilled water in order to make the combined mixture salt plus sugar plus alkali 15 c.c. The solution of caustic soda was then mixed with the salt solution. From the results to be presented later on, it was early observed that the total volume in which the peptisation is allowed to take place and the quantity of caustic soda used for forming the hydroxide affect the amount of sugar necessary to prevent the formation of a visible precipitate. It was therefore necessary to keep the volume constant at 15 c.c. in all the experiments, and the amount of alkali added was also kept constant. In all cases except that of iron, the solution remained clear on the addition of the mixture of water and alkali to the mixture of salt and sugar, if the requisite amount of sugar was present. But with ferric hydroxide it was observed that a solution which was at first turbid cleared up if the shaking was continued for some time. Consequently in the experiments with iron, the shaking was continued for five minutes in every case and the amount of sugar recorded in the tables against each quantity of iron is the minimum quantity necessary for the solution to become clear after five minutes of shaking. The results obtained are tabulated below in Tables I, II, III and IV.

TABLE I.

Peptisation of Copper Hydroxide.

Vol. = 15 c.c.; NaOH = 3 millimoles.

Copper chloride (in millimoles).	Amount of sugar necessary to prevent precipitation (in millimoles).			
	Sucrose	Dextrose	Lævulose	Lactose
0.1	0.0175
0.125	...	0.085	0.025	...
0.20	0.035
0.25	0.10	0.07	0.06	0.0475
0.35	0.11	0.075
0.375	0.19	0.095
0.45	0.11
0.50	0.25	0.15	0.20	0.135
0.60	0.25	0.19
0.625	0.34	0.28
0.70	...	0.38	...	0.24
0.75	0.64	0.45	0.35	0.275
0.85	0.45	...
0.875	1.05
0.95	0.57	...
1.0	2.7	...	0.60	>2.5
1.125	>4.5

TABLE II.

Peptisation of Ferric Hydroxide.

Vol. = 15 c.c.; NaOH = 3 millimoles.

Amount of FeCl ₃ (millimoles).	Amount of sugar necessary to prevent precipitation (in millimoles).			
	Sucrose.	Dextrose.	Lævulose.	Lactose.
0.0384	...	0.165
0.0668	0.31	...	0.045	0.15
0.0685	0.37	0.29
0.1336	0.09	0.205
0.167	0.55	0.46	0.10	0.325
0.2336	0.15	0.465
0.2505	0.77	0.65
0.3006	0.20	0.64
0.334	1.05	0.98	0.25	0.70
0.4006	0.40	1.80
0.4175	1.55	1.58
0.4675	0.565	1.925
0.501	2.1	2.0	0.64	2.40

TABLE III.

Peptisation of Mercurio Oxide.

Vol. = 15 c.c.; NaOH = 3 millimoles.

Amount of HgCl ₂ (millimoles).	Amount of sugar necessary to prevent precipitation (in millimoles).			
	Sucrose.	Dextrose.	Lævulose.	Lactose.
0.0338	0.19	0.40	0.17	0.17
0.0666	0.58	1.0	0.30	0.55
0.09996	0.99	1.65	0.61	0.96
0.1333	1.5	2.15	0.83	1.2
0.1666	2.1	2.85	1.2	1.45
0.1999	2.9	3.5	1.45	1.7
0.2332	3.7	4.0	1.75	2.05
0.2666	4.6	4.55	1.95	2.35
0.2999	5.65	5.2	2.3	...
0.3332	6.5	5.8	2.55	...
0.4165	3.25	...
0.4998	3.95	...

TABLE IV.

Peptisation of Cerium Hydrozide.

Vol. = 15 c.c.; NaOH = 3 millimoles.

Amount of CeCl ₃ (millimoles).	Amount of sugar necessary to prevent precipitation (millimoles).			
	Sucrose	Dextrose	Lævulose	Lactose
0.0166	...	1.0
0.0332	...	2.0	0.19	0.22
0.0498	...	3.05
0.0664	0.17	4.2	0.53	0.44
0.0830	...	>6.5
0.0996	1.1	0.65
0.1328	0.32	...	1.6	0.83
0.166	0.98	...	1.9	1.10
0.1826	1.22
0.1992	3.0	...
0.2324	0.56	...	3.7	1.565
0.2656	4.8	...
0.2822	1.875
0.2988	0.73	...	5.7	...
0.3320	0.77	...	>7.0	2.25
0.3684	0.90
0.4048	1.08
0.4980	1.20
0.5844	1.30
0.6306	2.66
0.6640	2.90

The curves have been drawn in a slightly different way, the ordinate being the concentration of one particular sugar whilst the abscissa represents the concentration of different salts. It is believed that the specific effect of sugars in the peptisation of different hydroxides will be better observed in this way. For purposes of illustration only one series of curves is given.

Discussion.

A glance at the curves given in Fig. I shows that in many cases the relation between the amount of hydroxide peptised and the amount of sugar necessary to prevent precipitation is a simple one, for in the cases of mercury and cerium (with three out of four sugars) the curves are straight lines. In the case of copper too, the earlier portion of the curve at low concentrations of the salt is almost a straight line. Consequently these curves can be represented by an equation of the type $C_s = A \cdot C_m + B$, where C_s is the amount of sugar in millimoles; C_m is the amount of metallic hydroxide in millimoles, and A and B are constants for the particular experiment. In the following table the values of A and B, and the limit within which the equation holds, are shown for various sugars.

TABLE V.

Sugar.	A	B	Metal.	Limits of salt concentration within which the equation is applicable. (in millimoles)
Dextrose	68.5	-0.25	Cerium	0.0166 to 0.0664
	18.4	-0.20	Mercury	0.0333 to 0.3332
	2.2	+0.10	Iron	0.0334 to 0.2505
	0.28	0.0	Copper	0.125 to 0.5
Sucrose	0.68	-0.075	Copper	0.25 to 0.625
	2.40	0.0	Cerium	0.0664 to 0.498
	2.50	+0.145	Iron	0.0668 to 0.2505
Lactose	6.8	-0.02	Cerium	0.0332 to 0.332
	0.21	-0.005	Copper	0.10 to 0.35
	2.1	+0.005	Iron	0.0668 to 0.334
	8.87	-0.0025	Mercury	0.0333 to 0.2666
Lævulose	0.404	-0.033	Copper	0.125 to 0.35
	8.33	-0.16	Mercury	0.0333 to 0.4998
	0.648	0.0	Iron	0.045 to 0.3006

It will be observed from this table that the values of B are often negative, and in several cases, notably with copper and dextrose, with cerium and sucrose, with iron and lævulose and practically with copper and iron and lactose, the values of B are zero. In other words, in these particular cases, the equation reduces to $C_s = A.C_m$, i.e., the amount of hydroxide peptised is directly proportional to the amount of sugar present within the limits of salt concentration given in the table.

It will be recalled that Graham called these peptised solutions of copper and iron as sucrates of copper and iron. As a matter of fact up to the concentrations in which, $C_m/C_s = \text{constant}$, we might indeed conceive that a really definite compound is formed. As soon as however one goes out of this particular concentration range, the relation $C_m/C_s = \text{constant}$ no longer holds, and therefore the probability of a definite chemical compound formation with a constant ratio of C_m/C_s breaks down. From Table V it will be observed that out of 14 cases, only 5 experiments can be represented by an equation of the type $C_m/C_s = k$. Since there is no reason to believe that the other experiments are absolutely different in nature from these five, it is obvious that in these five cases, the results are only accidental. To consider, however, this point of the probability of a compound formation more fully, the molecular ratio of metal to sugar has been calculated in the cases of copper and iron, and are given in the following tables.

TABLE VI.

Amount of iron (milli gr. atom) peptised.	Ratio of gr. atom iron to gr. mole sugar in the peptised state.			
	Sucrose.	Dextrose.	Lævulose.	Lactose.
0.0668	0.22	...	1.48	0.45
0.1670	0.80	0.86	1.67	0.51
0.3340	0.32	0.34	1.33	0.48
0.5010	0.24	0.25	0.78	0.21

TABLE VII.

Amount of Cu in milli gr. atom peptised.	Ratio gr. atom Cu to gr. mole sugar in the peptised state.			
	Sucrose.	Dextrose.	Lævulose.	Lactose.
0.25	2.5	3.57	4.16	5.26
0.50	2.0	3.33	2.5	3.70
0.625	1.84	2.28
0.75	1.17	1.66	2.14	2.8
1.00	0.87	...	0.33	<0.4

These results show that the ratio of metal atom to sugar is very variable and depends upon the actual amount of hydroxide peptised. From Table VII it appears that there is a gradual fall in the value of the ratio with increase in the actual amount of the peptised hydroxide, but with iron in Table VI no such relation is observable, for the ratio at first rises and reaching a maximum, decreases. It appears therefore that no simple relation exists between the two. The specific nature of sugars in the peptisation of hydroxides is also obvious from these tables, namely the variation in the values of this ratio with different sugars. From the curves it has been observed that the peptisability of the different hydroxides is in the same order in the case of dextrose, and lævulose, namely, $\text{Cu} > \text{Fe} > \text{Hg} > \text{Ce}$, but in the case of sucrose the order is $\text{Cu} > \text{Ce} > \text{Fe} > \text{Hg}$ and in that of lactose, it is $\text{Cu} > \text{Fe} > \text{Ce} > \text{Hg}$. This is of course the order when the results are expressed in moles, but will vary when the results are expressed in equivalents. It is curious also that the actual amount necessary to peptise a definite amount of hydroxide should be so very different in the case of dextrose and lævulose, and sucrose and lactose. This fact alone goes against the hypothesis of any definite chemical compound formation. In the following pages it will be shown that the actual volume of the solution in which the experiment is made, and the amount of alkali used have also a great effect on the amount of sugar necessary to peptise a definite amount of hydroxide.

Effect of Volume.

The experiments so far discussed were all done in a constant volume of 15 c.c. It was thought desirable at this time to make some experiments with different total volumes, to see whether any variation in the actual amount of sugar necessary to peptise a definite amount of hydroxide occurs or not. In the following two tables the results with copper and mercury are shown at two other volumes, 10 c.c. and 7 c.c. with sucrose only. The amount of alkali remains the same, namely 8 millimoles. For the sake of comparison, the ratio of metal to sugar is shown at all the volumes.

TABLE VIII.

Amount of Cu (milli gr. atom) peptised.	Millimoles of sucrose.		Ratio Cu/Sugar		
	Vol.=10 c.c.	Vol.=7 c.c.	Vol.=7 c.c.	Vol.=10 c.c.	Vol.=15 c.c.
0.125	0.05	0.05	2.5	2.5	...
0.25	0.11	0.115	2.17	2.28	2.5
0.375	0.195	0.20	1.87	1.92	...
0.50	0.265	0.32	1.56	1.88	2.0]
0.625	0.40	0.47	1.33	1.56	1.84
0.75	0.90	1.00	0.75	0.83	1.17

TABLE IX.

Amount of Hg (milli gr. atom) peptised.	Millimoles of sucrose.		Ratio Hg/Sugar.		
	Vol.=10 c.c.	Vol.=7 c.c.	Vol.=7 c.c.	Vol.=10 c.c.	Vol.=15 c.c.
0.0833	0.3	0.34	0.098	0.111	0.175
0.0666	0.69	0.82	0.081	0.096	0.115
0.0999	1.2	1.45	0.068	0.083	0.101
0.1333	1.7	2.35	0.056	0.075	0.088
0.1666	2.85	>3	<0.055	0.071	0.079

It will be apparent from Tables VIII and IX that the volume of the solution has no appreciable effect when the amount of metal ion is very small, but at moderate concentrations of the salts, the volume in which peptisation is studied has a decided effect on the amount of sugar necessary to peptise the hydroxide. Thus it will be observed, in both the tables, that the ratio of metal to sugar gradually increases, as the volume of the solution increases. In other words, less of sugar is necessary to peptise a definite amount of copper and mercury hydroxide at higher volumes than that required to peptise at lower volumes. It is difficult to give a satisfactory explanation of this phenomenon, but it appears that for each volume of solution and amount of sugar, there is a maximum amount of colloid which can be retained by the system.

Effect of Amount of Alkali.

It has already been mentioned that the amount of sugar necessary to prevent precipitation of a certain quantity of any hydroxide depends upon the actual amount of alkali present in the system. A further study of the phenomenon was, therefore, made with mercuric chloride and copper chloride in presence of sucrose. The results are given below in Tables X and XI. The total volume was 15 c.c.

TABLE X.

Amount of copper (milli gr. atom) peptised.	Millimoles of sucrose.		
	NaOH=2 milli- moles.	NaOH=3 milli- moles.	NaOH=5 milli- moles.
0.125	0.05	—	0.04
0.250	0.14	0.10	0.10
0.375	0.20	0.19	0.175
0.500	0.31	0.25	0.23
0.625	0.35	0.34	0.32
0.750	>8.0	0.64	0.55

TABLE XI.

Amount of Hg (milli gr. atom) peptised.	Millimoles of sucrose.		
	NaOH=1.5 milli- moles.	NaOH=3 milli- moles.	NaOH=5 milli- moles.
0.0333	0.19	0.19	0.25
0.0666	0.42	0.58	0.62
0.0999	0.81	0.90	1.05
0.1333	1.20	1.50	1.58
0.1666	1.70	2.10	2.20
0.2332	5.7	6.50	—

From these tables it will be observed that the influence of the change in the amount of alkali is not appreciable at lower concentrations of the salts studied, specially copper. In the case of mercury, however, when only 1.5 millimoles of alkali are present, the difference in the values of sucrose necessary to prevent precipitation from those required when 3 millimoles of alkali are present becomes obvious even at low concentrations. This remarkable difference is probably due to the coagulating effect of caustic soda on mercuric oxide at higher concentrations of the alkali. A similar effect may account for the higher values of sucrose when the total volume is less than 15 c.c. in the case of mercury. The behaviour of copper, however, does not seem to fit in with such an explanation. The results in the case of smaller volumes are quite intelligible on the explanation put forward above. But the values of sucrose found to be sufficient to check precipitation of copper hydroxide when larger quantities of alkali are used appear to contradict this suggestion. According to this view, one would expect higher amounts of sugar to be necessary when 5 millimoles of alkali are used than when only 3 millimoles are present. But on the contrary, the amount found is actually less than that in the case of 3 millimoles of alkali. In other words, with greater amounts of alkali there is a peptising action noticeable. Attention may also be drawn to another interesting point. From Table X it may be observed that even 8 millimoles of sucrose failed to prevent the formation of a visible precipitate from 0.75 milligram atom of copper when 2 millimoles of

alkali are used, but when 3 millimoles of alkali are present, 0.64 millimoles of sucrose are quite efficient to check the formation of a visible precipitate. This shows that to prevent by means of a sugar the appearance of a precipitate of a metallic hydroxide, it is not sufficient that a certain amount of alkali be present in excess than is required to form the hydroxide of the metal, but it is essential that a certain minimum excess of alkali be present.

Time Effect on Peptisation.

As already stated in the case of iron, there appears to be a time factor in the phenomenon of peptisation. In the case of copper as well, it was noticed that at higher concentrations of the salt the peptisation was not immediate, but it required shaking for a minute or two. The solution became clear even if the test tube was set aside for a while. In both the cases of iron and copper, shaking probably helps in the mechanical disintegration of the precipitate. In the case of mercury the reverse phenomenon occurred. It was noticed in the experiments that although the solutions remained clear on the addition of alkali to the mixture of salt and the requisite amount of sugar, a precipitate of mercuric oxide appeared on standing for some time, unless there was great excess of sugar. With increasing amount of sugar, the time of appearance of the precipitate also increased.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) An experimental study has been made of the peptisation of the hydroxides of copper, iron, mercury and cerium in presence of sucrose, dextrose, laevulose and lactose in various concentrations.

(2) The effect of sugars is a specific one and there is a marked difference between sucrose and lactose, and dextrose and laevulose in the power of preventing the precipitation of hydroxides.

(3) With dextrose and laevulose, the order of peptisation of different chlorides comes in the series $\text{Cu} > \text{Fe} > \text{Hg} > \text{Ce}$, but with sucrose the series is $\text{Cu} > \text{Ce} > \text{Fe} > \text{Hg}$, and with lactose $\text{Cu} > \text{Fe} > \text{Ce} > \text{Hg}$.

(4) The volume of the solution and the amount of alkali used have great effects on the minimum amount of sugars necessary to prevent precipitation of hydroxides. It is always necessary to have

a minimum excess of alkali present. In some cases, turbid mixtures become clear on standing, but in the case of mercury, the reverse may happen.

(5) In the case of several experiments it was found that the amount of hydroxide peptised was directly proportional to the amount of sugar present, but this is not general. The ratio of metal to sugar is variable depending upon the amount of the hydroxide peptised, the volume of the solution and the amount of alkali present, and hence there is no possibility of a definite chemical compound formation between the hydroxide and the sugar.

In conclusion, a few remarks may be made as to the probable way in which the sugar and alkali afford the protection which has been observed. It is generally admitted that the peptisation is usually preceded by adsorption of the protecting substance by the substance peptised. Bancroft (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1916, 20, 85) has suggested that peptisation in general is brought about as a result of the lowering of the surface tension of the adsorbing material on account of the adsorbed substance and consequently believes that peptisation may result as a sequel of the adsorption of even non-electrolytes or undissociated salt molecules. In a recent paper one of us has discussed the theory of peptisation in detail. (Sen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1533) There is no question that sugars are adsorbed by the hydroxides and the mechanism of sugar adsorption by several colloids has been considered by some authors (Bhatnagar and collaborators, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 20, 730; 1925, 19, 166) to be chemical in nature. This fact of the adsorption of sugar alone, however, does not explain the mechanism of the peptisation of the hydroxides. Thus it has been shown in this paper that the peptisation of the hydroxides observed is clearly affected by the amount of alkali employed. Not only is the amount of sugar necessary to prevent the formation of a visible precipitate controlled by the change in the quantity of alkali present but a certain minimum excess of alkali is necessary before any amount of sugar added can check the formation of a visible precipitate. This clearly indicates that the part of the alkali in bringing about the peptisation of the hydroxides is of great importance. It is probable that in presence of excess of alkali, the adsorption of sugar may be decreased, and hence greater amounts of sugars would be necessary to prevent precipitation of the hydroxides. As already stated, the results with copper, however, point to the exactly opposite conclusion. Hence the effect of alkali cannot be explained by simply connecting it with its

probable influence on the adsorption of sugar by the hydroxide particles.

It will be interesting to note here that these peptised solutions are only stable in presence of an excess of acid or alkali. Thus ferric hydroxide is stable both in acid and alkaline medium whereas copper hydroxide is peptised when the solution is alkaline. When alkali is added gradually to a mixture of ferric chloride and sugar, there is no formation of a precipitate but at the same time no test of free alkali is obtainable in the solution. What happens is that at first a positively charged colloid is formed. Owing to the presence of undecomposed ferric chloride, the stability is quite high, but with the gradual addition of alkali, the charge diminishes and the colloid ultimately coagulates. If the hydroxyl ion concentration is still more increased, the coagulum dissolves forming a negatively charged sol. This coagulation and stabilisation into either positively or negatively charged sol can be brought about as many times as desired by simply adding suitable quantities of either acid or alkali. Since this is so, the question arises, what is the function of sugar in this case of peptisation? That the non-electrolyte has some action is evident from the fact that we do not get usually a negatively charged ferric hydroxide with caustic soda unless precautions are observed (*Cf. Powis, J. Chem. Soc., 1915, 107, 818*). On the other hand sugar does not stabilise the colloid in the absence of a minimum excess of H^c or OH' ions.

We are consequently of opinion that in the cases studied in this paper where excess of alkali has always been used, the observed peptisation is the combined result of the presence of both alkali and sugars, and in any interpretation of the mechanism of the inhibition of the precipitation of metallic hydroxides in presence of sugars, the effect of the excess of alkali has also to be considered as at least of equal if not of more importance than the sugars. (See, in this connection, *Sen, J. Phys. Chem., 1925, 29, 1546*).

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Received November 8, 1926.

